

The Design of an Illustration Book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah' For Teenagers as an Introduction of Central Java's Traditional Food

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ABSTRACT: Indonesia is a country that has a vast territory and creates the characteristics of each area. Having many regions with different cultures gives a various flavors of food typical of each region. However, due to the times, some of these traditional foods have become extinct. In this design it aims to create an educational medium for teenagers about traditional Central Javanese food in the form of an illustration book. The research method used in this design is descriptive qualitative which has the characteristics of being a direct data source, descriptive in nature, more concerned with processes than results, carried out by means of inductive analysis, and meaning is essential. The research data were obtained from the bibliography, data from traditional snack traders, and responses from SMA Batik 2 Surakarta students as well as responses from teenagers in several areas in Central Java. The concept of this design is to prepare reading topics and narratives, create storylines, create character concepts, visual and non-visual concepts, make illustration sketches and layouts, and a series of financial plans to create an illustration book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah' with physical book as the primary media. As for supporting media as information and publication media, namely in the form of posters, tumblrs, stickers, key chains, and Instagram social media.

KEYWORDS –Illustration Book, Traditional Foods, Central Java

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a country that has a variety of delicious and unique culinary delights. Indonesian food is much-loved, some of which are even included in the top list of the most delicious foods in the world (Hens, 2019). One area in Indonesia that has an interesting culinary taste is Java Island. Java Island is one of the largest islands and the busiest island in Indonesia which continues to experience development. In addition to its culture, the island of Java also has a public appeal in terms of various culinary delights.

The island of Java itself has many regions, such as West Java, Central Java and East Java, each of which is further divided into regional sections and has its own special food. This is what makes the island of Java produce a lot of special foods. At least in the three provinces of Java Island there are around 300 more special foods in just one province. However, due to the times, many traditional foods from each region have undergone modernization so that they are no longer original, some have even disappeared.

Modern food is traded more in restaurants and food stalls than traditional food. Traditional food itself is usually only sold in traditional markets and only at certain hours and is not available all the time, for example only in the morning or evening. This is because traditional food itself does not have a long shelf life, considering that traditional food does not use a lot of preservatives and does not even use preservatives at all.

Because it is available in a limited place and time, the introduction of traditional food to the surrounding community is uneven. According to the results research conducted by the Health Education Authority in 2013, aged 15-34 years are the most consumers who choose the fast food menu. Teenagers only

know a few traditional foods. The introduction of this traditional food is usually only known by young people through weddings, traditional ceremonies, and others. In everyday life, teenagers often consume modern foods such as junk food. With the emergence of restaurants serving fast food, snacks from outside are considered more prestigious than traditional snacks (Widodo, 2013:435). Even though traditional food itself does not only function as a staple food ingredient, but also becomes a symbol of the identity of a region (Nurhayati, 2013: 8). In addition, according to FKKMK UGM Health Nutrition Expert, Lily Arsanti explained that the increase in the number of people with diabetes mellitus was partly due to the high level of consumption of sugar in modern foods. This is different from traditional foods such as gatot and tiwul which contain complex carbohydrates and low sugar levels and do not contain preservatives and other chemicals so that they are safe for consumption by the public.

Based on the problems described above, media is needed that can provide complete but light knowledge to the public as a source of information about the rich flavors of traditional food in Java. According to Hurlock (1978: 337) there are 3 types of reading media, namely books, newspapers and magazines. Among the three types of media, illustrated books are considered suitable as a medium for introducing typical foods in Java. Illustration itself has the meaning as a decoration with a picture or making something clear. Usually the use of illustrations in books uses cartoon form (Nurhadiat, 2004). Illustrated books contain several colorful pictures that look more attractive and easy to understand than textbooks alone. Illustrations make it easier for readers to remember a concept or idea conveyed (Kusrianto, 2009). Therefore, the media used by the author is an illustrated book, besides being more interesting it also overcomes the lack of disinformation if only using textbooks.

The illustrated book 'Miscellaneous Taste of Central Java' which has been made contains complete and interesting material about typical foods found on the island of Java, especially in the Province of Central Java. Using the province of Central Java because in this province there are various kinds of traditional culinary that are not fully known by outsiders. Considering that Central Java also has many famous cultural sites such as palaces, temples and other cultural sites, this province has many tourists. This is what made the author choose the province of Central Java to introduce its culinary specialties as well as other cultures so that tourists can get to know Central Java through culinary delights. Apart from that, it is also aimed at the local community with the aim that the culinary specialties of Central Java do not drown amid the proliferation of culinary delights from other countries. This book will be made with illustrations to attract the attention of the public, especially teenagers to broaden their knowledge of Central Javanese cuisine.

II. METHODE

To be able to conduct research required data collection and data analysis. The research methodology used for design uses qualitative methods which have the characteristics of being a direct data source, descriptive in nature, more concerned with process than results, carried out by means of inductive analysis, and meaning is essential. The research strategy itself includes data collection techniques, data processing techniques, and data analysis techniques.

In this research, primary and secondary data collection was carried out. Primary data obtained from direct interviews and distributing questionnaires. Interviews regarding traditional Central Javanese food were conducted with several traditional hawker traders in traditional markets. For questionnaires distributed online and offline. Offline questionnaires were distributed to SMA Batik 2 Surakarta students and online questionnaires were distributed to teenagers who live in the Central Java region. Secondary data was obtained from literature obtained from several books and journals as well as related articles. The subjects of the study were early adolescents to late adolescents aged 12-22 years, while the object of the study was an illustrated book containing traditional Central Javanese food. The method used for data collection in the study used observation techniques using information from books and online, as well as collecting questionnaires with respondents who were teenagers who live on the island of Java.

III. DISCUSSION

3.1 Illustration Book

The book comes from the Greek language with the initial word biblio which means library or book (Suwarno, 2011). According to the Indonesian Encyclopedia, a book in a broad sense includes all the writings and pictures written or depicted on various kinds of papyrus, parchment, papyrus, and paper in various forms. Books are a tool used to convey information quite effectively, this is because books can convey a lot of information because books have many pages (Rustan, 2009: 122).

According to UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization), it is argued that books have a meaning in the form of the main vehicle for information, research for sources of civilization and recreation, helping to drive national development, enriching individual lives, maintaining a feeling of mutual respect among nations who have differences in nationality and culture, as well as strengthening each individual's desire for peace. From this statement it can be concluded that books are the main tool for humans in exchanging information and research for education (Suwarno, 2011).

Illustrative images are images that are explanatory or are visualizations of a description, either in the form of news, stories, essays, or manuscripts (Alwi, 2002). Illustrative images also have a meaning, namely a brief description of the storyline of a story that aims to further explain a scene (Kusmiyati, 2009). Meanwhile, according to Putra and Lakoro (2012: 2), illustrations in a book have the purpose of explaining or decorating a story, writing, poetry, or other text information.

3.2 Traditional Foods

Traditional food is food that has many characteristics where a person is born and grows (Winarno, 1994). Traditional food can also be interpreted as food and drink that is commonly consumed by certain people in a certain area, with a taste that is accepted by that community. The role of culture is very concerned in the manufacture of traditional food, such as aspects of creativity, artistic touch, tradition and taste. The quality of a particular regional culture will produce the same quality of traditional food and drink, the higher the quality, the more unique and complicated the production will be. The attractiveness of food such as taste, color, shape and texture plays an important role in food evaluation (Soekarto, 1990).

Traditional food is made from ingredients obtained locally according to local people's tastes and traditions and follows the rules and recipes that have been passed down from generation to generation. These foods are usually consumed more by the local people of origin and then introduced to the outside community. Traditional food which is part of the culture of society can be developed as a tourism product to attract tourists. For example, one of the things that attracts tourists in Central Java is its traditional food. Apart from its culture and crafts, of course outsiders will be curious about the taste of Central Javanese food. The introduction of traditional food is not only through tourism media, but also through cultural education media in the form of a collection of knowledge about traditional Central Javanese food which is compiled in a book.

3.3 Interview Result

In designing the illustrated book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah', interviews were conducted with several traditional food vendors in traditional markets. The traders were named Mr. Yudi and Mr. Parmin. He has been selling traditional food for more than 20 years. Traditional food is sold more in traditional markets than in modern markets, this is because traditional food does not last long because it does not use preservatives at all. Traditional food usually lasts only 1-2 days. However, this is what people like because food that only lasts a few days seems fresher because every day is always new than modern food that can be stored longer. According to the informant, basically traditional Central Javanese food has three types or categories, namely heavy food, traditional snacks, and traditional drinks. Because the manufacture and recipes have been passed down from ancient times, this food has its own meaning in every preparation and ingredients used.

In addition to conducting interviews with traditional snack traders, the authors also made observations through online and offline questionnaires. From the observations that have been made, it is known that the majority of Batik 2 Surakarta High School students already know what traditional food is, both Central Javanese food and food outside Central Java. All respondents not only know what traditional food is, but they have also tasted traditional food quite frequently. Teenagers most often encounter traditional food in traditional markets. In addition, they also find traditional food during certain events, such as traditional ceremonies, invitations, festivities, and others. Not a few also find traditional food at home. The frequency of adolescents consuming traditional food ranges from one to seven days on average, but not a few consume it every day.

For the second observation, the researcher conducted an online questionnaire which was conducted using the Google Form. In this questionnaire, researchers took a random sample of adolescents who live in Central

Java, with an age range of 14-22 years. The number of respondents who have been collected from this questionnaire is 73 respondents with details of 14% aged 15 years, 14% aged 16 years, 23% aged 17 years, 5% aged 18 years, 5% aged 20 years, 29% aged 21 years, and 10% are 22 years old.

picture 3. 1 The results of the questionnaire on adolescent interest in traditional food

From the two observations that have been made, it shows that teenagers' interest in traditional food is very high, in fact almost all of them like traditional food. But there are some traditional foods that teenagers don't like. Some foods that have a high frequency of dislike by teenagers are gethuk, bothok, brambangtamarind, cenil, tofu petis, tiwul, and others. If you pay attention, the average traditional food that is not liked by teenagers is very traditional food and has a striking difference in taste with other foods. Meanwhile, traditional food that is liked by teenagers, on average, is food that is commonly consumed by the community, even as food for daily consumption. Traditional foods that teenagers like are tempemendoan, lumpia Semarang, solo sausage, liwet rice, kupat tofu, pecel, putu cake, and others. Even though there are traditional foods that are disliked and liked by teenagers, it is possible if there are teenagers who like foods that are usually disliked, and vice versa.

picture 3. 2 The results of the questionnaire on the frequency of adolescents consuming traditional food

Based on the questionnaire, as many as 21% of teenagers eat traditional Central Javanese food every day. These traditional foods are usually in the form of staple foods or vegetables which are used for daily meals. Most adolescents consume typical Central Javanese food within one to seven days, that is as much as 57%. Meanwhile, 22% of teenagers eat traditional food once a month. It can be concluded that teenagers prefer to make traditional food as a distraction and not make it a staple food.

3.4 Conceptual Design

In designing an illustrated book on traditional Central Javanese food entitled 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah', a good visual communication medium is needed so that it can be easily accepted and understood by the wider community so that the purpose of making the book is achieved. There are several aspects that need to be considered in designing creative concepts in order to reach the target market and attract the attention of the audience.

Based on the data obtained from the 104 questionnaire respondents collected, there were 76 people who had an interest in reading books with only a few books of a certain genre, 9 people only liked textbooks, 3 people had no interest in reading books, and 16 people who had an interest in reading all types of book genres. Of the 101 respondents who had an interest in reading books, 43 people liked text books only and 64 people liked books with illustrations.

Illustration

Based on the questionnaire that was distributed to 104 respondents, in choosing an illustration style the values are not much different. A total of 25 people chose flat illustrations without outlines, 23 people chose illustrations with thin outlines, 29 people chose illustrations with anime style, and 30 people chose illustrations without outlines and have texture. Even without an outline, this style illustration has contrasting color differences in each part so it doesn't look confusing. In the illustrated book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah', there is a fictional character named Ajeng. This character will guide the reader in exploring the contents of the book.

picture 3. 3 Style illustration option D

picture 3. 4Ajeng Character

Typography

Based on the results of the questionnaire that has been collected from 104 respondents regarding fonts, as many as 53 people choose serif type fonts to be used as headlines or titles, 18 people choose sans serif fonts, and 30 people choose decorative fonts. For the bodytype, 42 people chose a serif font, 50 people chose a sans-serif font, and 8 people chose a decorative font.

picture 3. 5 The results of the font style questionnaire

The typography used in the illustration book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah' is a light font and not too stiff or formal. This is because the target market is teenagers who are flexible and free. Based on the results of the questionnaire, the results obtained were the use of a serif font for the title and a sans-serif font for the body text. The font used is Purple Purse for the headline and Neucha font for the bodyline.

Aa	Bb	Cc	Dd	Ee	Ff
Gg	Hh	Ii	Jj	Kk	Ll
Mm	Nn	Oo	Pp	Qq	Rr
Ss	Tt	Uu	Vv	Ww	Xx
Yy	Zz	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	0

Aa	Bb	Cc	Dd	Ee	Ff
Gg	Hh	Ii	Jj	Kk	Ll
Mm	Nn	Oo	Pp	Qq	Rr
Ss	Tt	Uu	Vv	Ww	Xx
Yy	Zz	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	0

picture 3. 6 Font style

Color

Based on the results of the questionnaires that had been collected, the selection of color tones for the illustration book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah' was chosen to use warm tones. The color palette uses four basic colors with the addition of other colors as supporters.

#3F4238

#A94C4C

#B98C74

#FEE7D6

Layout

Based on the results of the questionnaire, the layout style used in the illustration book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah' is the Axial Layout style. The layout used is to focus on the illustration in the middle and the information text on the edges. In designing this illustration book, the first page will be filled with illustrations and brief information. The next page contains rather long information with small illustrations. One piece of traditional food will take up 2 pages.

picture 3. 7 Layout style

Logos

In designing the illustrated book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah', a display was needed that would become the hallmark of the product. Therefore, a logo was created that would be placed on book covers and various other merchandise. This logo uses the Purple Purse typeface with green and red colors with warm tones.

picture 3. 8 Illustration book logo 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah'

IV. CONSLUSION

This design is intended for the creation of a work in the form of an illustrated book 'Serba-Serbi Rasa Jawa Tengah' with the form of a physical book as the main medium and is aimed at teenagers who are domiciled in Central Java. The illustrated book is designed in a rectangular shape measuring 20 cm x 25 cm, totaling 42 pages where the book contains text accompanied by illustrations. The illustrations used are cartoon style without outlines with digital art techniques. The concept of the design is made using a casual and relaxed style with warm color tones so that it makes the reader comfortable in exploring the contents of the book. The font used for the headline uses the Purple Purse font and the font for the bodyline uses the Neucha font. This design uses supporting media such as posters, Tumblrs, stickers, key chains, and Instagram social media.

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